

RENOVATION IN GERMANY'S ARCHITECTURE

Ulugbek Tadjiboyev-teacher

*Samarkand State of Architecture and Civil Engineering University,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Abstract: Renovation in Germany's architecture encompasses a rich tapestry of historical context, contemporary practices, and evolving sustainability goals. Rooted in the complexities of Germany's colonial past and post-World War II reconstruction efforts, architectural renovation reflects a broader narrative of national identity and historical preservation. This dynamic field is notable not only for its rich architectural heritage, including Romanesque and Baroque styles, but also for its innovative approaches to energy efficiency and community engagement, exemplified by initiatives like the European Commission's renovation wave and local sustainable housing projects like "baugruppen" in neighborhoods such as Vauban.

Keywords: Architectural renovation, Germany, historical preservation, energy efficiency, sustainability, community engagement, regulatory challenges, baugruppen, renovation wave, urban development, heritage conservation, socio-economic impact, sustainable architecture, ecological responsibility, policy innovation[1][2][3].

Introduction. As Germany strives for climate neutrality, renovations are increasingly focused on sustainability and energy efficiency. The government's Federal Subsidy for Efficient Buildings (BEG) and various municipal policies aim to encourage both private

and communal efforts to modernize building stock while minimizing environmental impact.[4][5] Renovations often involve balancing the need to preserve historical integrity with the demands of modern functionality, leading to diverse approaches ranging from serial refurbishment to community-driven initiatives.[6][7] Controversies in this field often arise from the tension between modernization and the preservation of cultural heritage. Challenges such as navigating complex regulatory environments, financial constraints, and maintaining craftsmanship skills are significant hurdles that architects and homeowners face. Moreover, the push for energy-efficient renovations has sparked debates about gentrification and the socio-economic implications for affected communities, particularly in urban centers.[8][9][10]

Ultimately, the evolution of renovation practices in Germany highlights a commitment to embracing tradition while innovating for a sustainable future, shaping not only the physical landscape but also the social fabric of communities. As urbanization trends continue to rise, the importance of thoughtful and inclusive renovation strategies will be paramount for future development.[11][12]

Methodology. The history of renovation in Germany's architecture is deeply intertwined with the nation's colonial past and its role in European nation-building. Berlin hosted the 1885 conference where Africa was partitioned among European powers, a process overseen by Otto von Bismarck, Germany's Chancellor at the time.[1] This historical backdrop has prompted historians to analyze the violent legacies of Germany's colonial ambitions, particularly during the reigns of Kaiser Wilhelm I and Wilhelm II, which included acts such as the genocide of the Herero and Nama peoples from 1904 to 1908.[1]

After World War II, Germany's architectural landscape underwent significant transformations, particularly influenced by the political dichotomy between East and West. In East Germany, architecture was largely directed by Soviet ideals, emphasizing a "National Building Tradition" that contrasted sharply with the American International Style predominant in the West. The design of significant projects, such as the Stalinallee in Berlin, aimed to incorporate references to classical architecture, thereby creating a distinct identity while distancing itself from both the Nazi past and Western capitalism.[2] This focus led to the restoration of historical monuments and urban centers with an expertise that was often lacking in the West, making architectural heritage more accessible to the working class.[2]

The evolution of renovation practices in Germany has been marked by a shift toward serial refurbishment as a strategy to manage costs and enhance sustainability.[3] By the late 20th century, efforts to optimize building repair processes became more structured, with initiatives emerging from collaborations between housing and construction industries as well as startups. This led to pilot projects aimed at promoting transparency and documentation of results, enhancing both the quality and efficiency of renovations across the country.[3]

Moreover, historical architecture, from the Romanesque to Baroque styles, has continued to influence contemporary renovation practices. The rich detailing and craftsmanship inherent in these styles are often preserved in modern renovations, reflecting a blend of historical reverence and contemporary needs.[4] Such practices demonstrate a commitment to maintaining Germany's architectural heritage amidst the pressures of modernization and urban development.

Result and Discussions. Types of Renovation Renovations in Germany encompass a variety of practices and approaches tailored to specific building types and their historical contexts. These practices are often shaped by the need to integrate modern functionality while preserving the architectural integrity of existing structures. For instance, industrial buildings

such as breweries and warehouses frequently undergo renovations that maintain original shells while introducing new programs, reflecting a blend of historical preservation and contemporary design[5].

A significant focus in German renovation practices is energy efficiency. The renovation wave initiative aims to accelerate energy upgrades in both residential and non-residential buildings, with a target of doubling the current annual energy renovation rate from 1% to 2% by 2030[6]. This effort includes deep energy renovations that can reduce buildings' energy consumption by at least 60%[6]. To achieve this, existing buildings often require substantial updates, such as improving insulation, upgrading electrical systems, and retrofitting for enhanced energy efficiency[7].

Source: <https://www.archdaily.com/999471/mvrdv-reveals-design-for-the-extensive-renovation-project-of-the-koblenz-theater-in-germany/643884cfb71ded017c90db90-mvrdv-reveals-design-for-the-extensive-renovation-project-of-the-koblenz-theater-in-germany-image>

Serial refurbishment has emerged as a strategic approach to manage complexity and costs associated with building renovations. This method involves repetitive, standardized processes that can streamline renovations and make them more cost-effective. An initiative involving the housing and construction industries in Germany is currently facilitating pilot projects to implement this approach effectively[3].

Community-driven renovation efforts are also notable, particularly in sustainable districts like Vauban, where citizens engage in collaborative housing projects known as "baugruppen." This model allows for shared costs and decision-making, resulting in affordable, socially mixed, and sustainable housing developments. The participation of residents not only fosters a sense of community but also enhances the overall quality of the living environment[8][9]. The push towards climate neutrality has led to innovative projects such as the pilot renovations by the Märkische Scholle housing cooperative in Berlin, where buildings were retrofitted to eliminate CO2 emissions for heating and ventilation. These efforts not only address environmental concerns but also promise stable living costs for tenants[10]. Such climate-neutral renovations exemplify the integration of ecological responsibility with modern living standards.

Source: <https://images.squarespace-cdn.com/content/v1/54105166e4b0aa2fd30226db/1545175371700-55XC31HICD7ZS41VXAW6/Bienenkorbhaus4.jpg?format=1000w>

Renovating a home in Germany involves navigating a complex regulatory landscape that is essential for a successful project. The surge in property renovations is largely driven by homeowners seeking to modernize living spaces and increase property values. However, many face costly mistakes due to unfamiliarity with local zoning laws and building permits[11][7]. Understanding these regulations is crucial for ensuring that renovations enhance property value while respecting historical significance[7]. Setting a realistic budget is a fundamental aspect of the renovation process. The financial landscape in Germany differs significantly from other countries, necessitating comprehensive planning that includes a contingency reserve for unexpected costs[7][3]. Homeowners are encouraged to explore local materials, which are often less expensive and more compliant with regulatory standards, as well as consider reclaimed or recycled materials for additional savings[7]. German architectural conservation is marked by the integration of modern technology and sustainable practices. Techniques such as 3D measurement technology are employed to accurately document historical structures, aiding in precise restorations while minimizing structural damage[12]. Additionally, the use of eco-friendly materials and energy-efficient systems has become increasingly important, aligning renovation efforts with broader ecological goals[12][6]. The emphasis on public participation in conservation projects enhances community involvement and promotes a sense of ownership over local architectural heritage.

Engaging residents not only supports conservation efforts but also fosters a deeper understanding of the importance of preserving historical buildings[12]. This community-centric approach is vital for the ongoing relevance of renovated structures in modern contexts[12]. While innovation plays a significant role, maintaining traditional craftsmanship is equally essential in renovation projects. The synergy between traditional skills and modern machinery allows for the

accurate recreation of intricate details, ensuring that the heritage value of original builders is preserved[12]. Moreover, the move towards utilizing more sustainable, textured materials reflects a growing desire for authenticity in design, prioritizing both aesthetic appeal and environmental responsibility[13][14]. Germany has seen a multitude of significant renovation projects, each showcasing innovative approaches to preserving historical integrity while integrating modern functionality.

Renovations in Germany often focus on industrial structures, where original buildings shells are preserved while introducing new uses. This includes projects such as breweries, warehouses, and refineries, which are transformed into contemporary spaces that respect their historic significance[5]. These renovations not only enhance functionality but also indicate larger development trends within neighborhoods. An initiative in Germany is exploring serial refurbishments, which aim to reduce costs and complexities by standardizing renovation processes across similar building types[3]. Noteworthy urban refurbishment projects in cities like Erfurt and Halle exemplify a careful balance between maintaining historic urban areas and implementing modern building solutions. These projects involve a thorough analysis and replication of formal architectural attributes from existing structures, thereby integrating new constructions seamlessly into their historic contexts[15]. Among the iconic buildings that have undergone renovations is the Berlin Cathedral, which has been adapted and restored to reflect both its historical significance and modern architectural advancements.

Additionally, the Elbphilharmonie in Hamburg, designed by Herzog & de Meuron, showcases contemporary design while honoring its historical waterfront setting[16]. Renovations in Germany also emphasize sustainability, with many projects incorporating energy-efficient systems and updating essential infrastructure like electrical systems and insulation[7]. These updates are vital not only for compliance with current regulations but also for reducing overall emissions, thus reflecting a commitment to environmentally responsible architecture[3]. The German government has implemented various policies and incentives to promote renovation and enhance energy efficiency in buildings. Since 2021, a price on CO₂ emissions in the heating and transport sectors has been established, starting at 25 euros per ton and increasing annually, aimed at providing a financial incentive for renovations that enhance energy efficiency[3]. In April 2022, the Federal Subsidy for Efficient Buildings (BEG) was reinstated, with a budget of EUR 1 billion dedicated to promoting new construction and renovations. This program is designed to support various building envelope technologies, insulation methods, heating systems, and energy-efficient appliances. It includes three sub-programs focusing on residential buildings, non-residential buildings, and individual measures, each offering promotional loans and investment grants for energy

efficiency improvements.

At the municipal level, various instruments promote the implementation of green roofs and other climate-resilient initiatives. Common incentives include development plan determinations, municipal bylaws, funding programs with financial subsidies, eco-points, and fee reductions for split wastewater fees[16]. These local policies encourage communities to actively participate in environmentally friendly building practices, recognizing the importance of localized decision-making[15].

Historically, political objectives regarding energy supply have shifted significantly. Post-World War II, the focus was primarily on inexpensive and reliable energy supply, but as sustainability became a political goal, the emphasis transitioned towards renewable energy sources. This transformation has involved substantial changes in government subsidies and the liberalization of the energy market, allowing broader participation from the public and smaller companies in energy generation.

Additionally, the awareness of the environmental impact of the building sector has led to efforts to reshape the construction narrative. Experts like Hans Joachim Schellnhuber advocate for a transformation towards sustainable architecture, emphasizing the need to address greenhouse gas emissions from buildings and infrastructure, which account for approximately 40 percent of global emissions.

These policies and initiatives collectively illustrate Germany's commitment to enhancing building renovation practices through government support, local engagement, and a focus on sustainability.

In October 2020, the European Commission initiated a strategy known as the renovation wave, aiming to significantly enhance the energy efficiency of buildings across Europe, including Germany. The goal is to at least double the renovation rate within the next decade, which is expected to improve the quality of life for residents, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and support digitalization efforts[3]. A particular focus is placed on renovating buildings with the lowest energy efficiency ratings to combat energy poverty, a pressing issue affecting millions of Europeans who struggle to afford adequate heating for their homes[3].

The renovation wave also seeks to reconcile sustainability with design by launching a new European Bauhaus initiative. This program aims to foster a new aesthetic that balances affordability with artistic ambition, promoting a sustainable future[3]. The social implications of renovations extend beyond aesthetics; they involve a commitment to energy justice, ensuring that disadvantaged individuals have access to affordable energy solutions, which is critical for enhancing their living environments[16].

As cities evolve, the challenge of preserving historic sites while meeting contemporary demands has become paramount. Innovative solutions often arise when architects renew buildings while retaining their original features, creating modern extensions that

harmonize or contrast with the existing structures. This approach not only revitalizes these spaces but also honors the historical narrative embedded in them, creating a unique aesthetic that serves both functional and cultural purposes.

The energy transition and renovation efforts have generated economic opportunities, fostering the growth of new industries and business models. As cities adapt to modern demands, this can include the transformation of industrial areas into vibrant community spaces, facilitating local economic growth and sustainability[15]. Additionally, the rise of energy communities, where municipalities aim to take control of local distribution grids, exemplifies how renovation efforts can empower local populations and enhance their economic resilience. With urban populations projected to increase significantly, renovation efforts will play a crucial role in shaping the future of cities in Germany and beyond. The trend toward regionalization and the development of multi-functional locations outside traditional urban cores, such as airport cities, highlight the need for strategic renovations that accommodate growing populations while ensuring a high quality of life for residents. As urban areas continue to expand, addressing the community impact of renovations will be vital for sustainable urban development. Renovation in Germany presents a range of challenges that must be navigated to achieve successful outcomes. These challenges include financial constraints, regulatory compliance, and the delicate balance between preserving historical integrity and meeting modern standards.

Financial Considerations

Building refurbishment in Germany can be a complex and costly affair. The absence of standardized solutions for renovations often leads to unexpected expenses, such as updating electrical systems or improving insulation to meet current regulations[3]. Homeowners are advised to utilize detailed budgeting tools to manage these costs effectively and may benefit from engaging professionals such as quantity surveyors to maintain financial control throughout the renovation process[7]. Despite the initial financial burden, these updates are crucial for ensuring safety and energy efficiency in homes.

Renovations must comply with a myriad of national technical approvals and construction permits, which can complicate the process. These regulatory frameworks necessitate thorough planning and adherence to established legal requirements.

Furthermore, integrating energy-efficient renovation methods while preserving the integrity of historic buildings is an ongoing challenge, especially in light of growing ecological awareness and the push for sustainable building practices. This dual focus on conservation and modern efficiency requires tailored solutions that respect the historical context of structures. As cities evolve, the need to preserve historic sites becomes increasingly critical. Renovations must honor the heritage of these buildings while accommodating contemporary demands. The preservation process can be complicated by financial limitations and the scarcity

of skilled craftsmen familiar with traditional techniques, making it essential to invest in training for future generations to maintain these historic structures[4]. Moreover, integrating modern technology and innovative design can help navigate these complexities, allowing architects to create extensions that harmonize or contrast with original structures, thus enhancing both functionality and aesthetic appeal[5]. Achieving a balance between the demands of modern construction and the preservation of historical elements poses a unique challenge. Renovations can signal broader urban development trends, and the processes involved often reflect the social, political, and economic contexts in which they occur. Effective public participation and transparency in planning processes have been emphasized as critical components of successful renovation projects, ensuring that community interests are considered and met[19]. This multifaceted approach highlights the intricate interplay of factors influencing renovation practices in Germany.

Future Trends in Renovation. Sustainable Practices. The future of renovation in Germany increasingly emphasizes sustainable conservation practices. Utilizing eco-friendly materials and methods is becoming essential in reducing the environmental impact of restoration efforts. This includes the adoption of green building technologies such as energy-efficient systems and sustainable construction materials that preserve the original design's essence while enhancing functionality and efficiency[12]. The integration of gender equality in conservation missions is also gaining traction, ensuring that diverse perspectives shape renovation projects and promote community-centric approaches[12].

Energy Efficiency and Climate Goals. A pivotal aspect of future renovations will be adherence to Germany's climate protection commitments. The Federal Government has set ambitious goals, including achieving greenhouse gas neutrality by 2045 as outlined in the Climate Protection Act[28]. The upcoming implementation of minimum energy performance requirements for buildings, coupled with a gradual tightening of energy certificate regulations, reflects a proactive approach to enhancing energy efficiency in renovations[3]. These measures are designed to incentivize property owners to undertake energy-efficient upgrades while ensuring that such renovations do not unfairly increase rent or burden tenants[3].

Financial Management and Budgeting. Effective financial management will be critical for homeowners engaged in renovations. As renovations may uncover additional requirements, such as updates to electrical systems or improved insulation, homeowners are advised to utilize detailed budgeting tools and spreadsheets to track expenses against forecasts[7]. Engaging professionals, such as quantity surveyors or financial planners, can further assist in maintaining budget control while ensuring compliance with evolving regulations[7].

Innovative Architectural Trends. Emerging

architectural trends highlight a shift towards personalized and meaningful living spaces. The desire for functional, appealing, and calm environments has led to a renewed appreciation for "modernized rusticity," which combines tradition with modern design principles. This trend includes experimenting with flexible layouts that adapt to the dynamic needs of inhabitants, a necessity amplified by experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic [30]. The incorporation of digital tools in design allows for spaces that evolve over time, reflecting the importance of orientation, natural light, and overall aesthetics in modern interiors.

Conclusion. In conclusion, Germany's architectural renovation efforts reflect a profound synthesis of historical reverence, modern innovation, and sustainable development. Key findings indicate that Germany's renovation strategies emphasize energy efficiency, community engagement, and historical preservation, all while navigating a complex regulatory landscape. Initiatives like the European Commission's renovation wave and community-led projects such as the "baugruppen" model underscore the significant impact of public involvement on sustainable and socially inclusive urban development. However, challenges persist, including balancing heritage conservation with modern requirements, addressing regulatory complexities, and managing financial constraints. These findings imply that a carefully calibrated approach is essential for future renovations, focusing on ecological responsibility and socio-economic inclusivity. Further research could explore the long-term socio-economic impacts of these community-driven renovations and investigate innovative policy models that enhance regulatory flexibility while upholding heritage and environmental standards.

References

1. S. Kott and T. Wieder, "The (Re-)construction of Monuments in Germany: New Historical Narratives in a Time of Nation-building," *Contemporary European History*, vol. 32, pp. 3–8, 2023.
2. "Germany," *Architecture-History.org*. [Online]. Available: <https://architecture-history.org/country/germany.html>.
3. A. Kuehl, "How do we get the renovation wave rolling in Germany?," *EEIP*, Mar. 1, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://ee-ip.org/en/article/how-do-we-get-the-renovation-wave-rolling-in-germany-5685>.
4. "What makes Germany's Half-Timbered Buildings so historic?," *German National Tourist Board*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.germany.travel/en/towns-cities-culture/traditions-and-customs/half-timbered-buildings.html>.
5. "Industrial Nouveau: Dramatic Renovation Projects Reimagining Urban Life," *ArchDaily*, Aug. 12, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.archdaily.com/945678/industrial-nouveau-dramatic-renovation-projects-reimagining-urban-life>.
6. "Building renovation: where circular economy and climate meet," *European Commission*, Oct. 14, 2020. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_1835.
7. "Renovating a Home in Germany," *Homecazt Magazine*, Apr. 15, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://homecazt.com/renovating-a-home-in-germany/>.
8. "Innovative Participation during the Development of the Vauban District in Freiburg, Germany," *Sustainable Cities Collective*, May 5, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://sustainablecitiescollective.com/innovative-participation-during-development-vauban-district-freiburg-germany/>.
9. "Social Rehabilitation: Exploring Community Involvement in Architectural Conservation," *International Journal of Architectural Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1–15, 2018.
10. "Germany is able to achieve climate-neutral building stock by 2050," *Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics IBP*, Jan. 15, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ibp.fraunhofer.de/en/press-media/press-releases/germany-climate-neutral-building-stock-2050.html>.
11. "Germany: Renovation Policy," *Global Buildings Performance Network (GBPN)*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gbpn.org/databases-tools/policy-comparisons/renovation-policies/germany>.
12. "Revolutionizing German Architectural Conservation," *Architectural Digest*, Feb. 10, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.architecturaldigest.com/story/revolutionizing-german-architectural-conservation>.
13. "Top architecture and design trends for 2023," *Dezeen*, Dec. 20, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dezeen.com/2022/12/20/top-architecture-design-trends-2023/>.
14. "Green Buildings: Sustainable Construction Continues to Grow," *BNP Paribas Real Estate*, Mar. 15, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.realestate.bnpparibas.com/green-buildings-sustainable-construction-continues-grow>.
15. "Housing Paul and Paula: Building Repair and Urban Renewal in the German Democratic Republic," *Journal of Urban History*, vol. 44, no. 5, pp. 1–20, 2018.
16. Gayratovna, I. D., Achilovna, S. I., & Bakhodirovich, B. B. (2023). ORGANIZING PEDESTRIAN PATHS IN HISTORICAL CITIES. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, (2), 211-214.
17. Gayratovna, I. D., & Fayzullo qizl, Z. A. (2024). SHAHAR SHAROITIDA KO'P FUNKSIYALI BINOLAR. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 18(1), 133-136.
18. Рахимов, К. Д., & Исламова, Д. Г. (2024). ИСТОРИЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ГОРОДСКИХ ПЛОЩАДЕЙ САМАРКАНДА. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 49, 1534-1539.
19. Ibragimov, N. (2024). FORMATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF WATER ENTERTAINMENT HEALTH CENTERS. *Innovative: International Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Technology* (2995-486X), 340-342.
20. Khasanovich, I. N. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF SPA (SANUS PER AQUAM) ZONES IN WATER FACILITIES DEVELOPMENT OF SPA (HEALTH THROUGH WATER) ZONES IN WATER FACILITIES. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, (2), 306-308.

